

Table of Contents

Sl. No.	Title	Page No.
1.	The chromatin features used to calculate order parameter that classify loops into compartments	1
2.	Theory of Fisher's Linear Discriminant Analysis	22
3.	ANOVA table for each trajectory parameter	25
4.	Pairwise comparisons between models for each trajectory parameter.	26

Supplementary Text 1: The chromatin features used to calculate order parameter that classify loops into compartments:

ENCODE project data (ENCODE Project Consortium 2012):

- DNA methylation at CpG sites Methyl Array data (GEO Accession: GSM999376), Methyl Reduced Representation Bisulfite Sequencing (RRBS) (GSM683906, GSM683927).
- ChIP-seq data for chemical modifications (methylation, acetylation) to the histone proteins, particularly: H3K4me3, H3K27ac, H3K9ac, H4K20me1, H3K4me1, H3K4me2, H3K79me2, H3K36me3, H3K27me3, H3K9me3 and H2AZ (histone alternative variant)
- ChIP-seq data for 87 chromatin binding proteins.
- Open chromatin data: DNase-seq, FAIRE-seq, ENCODE synthesis. It is ENCODE synthesis of evidence from different assays: DNase I hypersensitivity (HS), Formaldehyde-Assisted Isolation of Regulatory Elements (FAIRE), and chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP) for select regulatory factors (PolIII, CTCF, c-Myc). It indicates the regions of the DNA available for direct interaction with non-histone proteins and RNA.
- ENCODE genome segmentation: ChromHMM (Ernst and Kellis 2013), Segway (Hoffman et al. 2012), ENCODE synthesis (Hoffman et al. 2013), old ChromHMM method based only on histone modifications (Ernst et al. 2011).

Using two different unsupervised machine learning techniques (ChromHMM and Segway), the genome was automatically segmented into disjoint segments. Each segment belongs to one of a few specific genomic "states" which is assigned an intuitive label ('active' for promoters (also inactive promoters), enhancers, transcription-associated, insulators, 'repressed' for Polycomb repressed, 'heterochromatin' for heterochromatin, repetitive, copy number variation regions) Those methods used ENCODE ChIP-seq, DNase-seq, and FAIRE-seq data. Regions that were not assigned to 'heterochromatin' not 'repressed' classes by the segmentation methods went to 'active' class.

- RNA-seq transcription data

High-throughput experiments aside ENCODE project:

- ATAC-seq (Buenrostro et al. 2013) data. Assay for transposase-accessible chromatin using sequencing is an alternative method to detect open chromatin
- GRO-seq (Core et al. 2014), Bru-seq data (Wilson et al. 2015). Those are experiments that aim to identify transcription start sites from nascent RNA.
- GC genome percentage

All the data was for hg19 human genome assembly. The data are described in more details below together with their source links). The data can be also visualized on three-dimensional models of GM12878 chromatin (<http://3dgenome.cent.uw.edu.pl>).

General description of the feature ids.

Data type	Id header
H2A.Z	H001
H3K27ac	H002
H3K27me3	H003
H3K36me3	H006
H3K4me1	H009
H3K4me2	H010
H3K4me3	H011
H3K79me2	H014
H3K9ac	H015
H3K9me3	H016
H4K20me1	H017
GC Percentage	GCPe
Nascent RNA	N001-N002
Open chromatin	O001-O006
DNA methylation at CpG sites	D001-D003
RNA-seq	R001-R012
ENCODE genome segmentation	S001-S004
Transcription factor ChIP-seq	T001-T102

GC percentage

from hg19 genome assemble (mean value)

DNA methylation at CpG sites - Methyl Array

Description:

<http://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTrackUi?db=hg19&g=wgEncodeHaibMethyl450>

Suggested visualization parameter: score (column 5) in three categories.

1. methylated (score \geq 600)
2. partially methylated ($200 < \text{score} < 600$)
3. unmethylated ($0 < \text{score} \leq 200$) or NA (score = 0)

The score concern only first CpG in 50 nt regions.

Example lines:

chr16	53468112	53468162	cg00000029	577	+	53468112	53468162
	128,0,128						
chr3	37459206	37459256	cg00000108	913	+	37459206	37459256
	255,127,0						

chr3	171916037 255,127,0	171916087	cg00000109	870	+	171916037	171916087
chr1	91194674 0,0,205	91194724	cg00000165	123	-	91194674	91194724

GEO Accession: GSM999376

Machine learning [D001]: score (column 5); mean, sum

D001.methylated: score (column 5) > 600; fraction

Download: [D001]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeHaibMethyl450/wgEncodeHaibMethyl450Gm12878SitesRep1.bed.gz>

DNA methylation at CpG sites - Methyl Reduced Representation Bisulfite Sequencing (RRBS)

“The score in this track reports the number of sequencing reads obtained for each CpG, which is often called 'coverage'. The score is capped at 1000.”

Description:

<http://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTrackUi?db=hg19&g=wgEncodeHaibMethylRrbs>

Suggested visualization threshold: score >=10

Suggested visualization parameter: percentage of methylated (column 11)

Machine learning [D002][D003]: column 11 with score (column 5) >=10; mean, sum

Example lines:

```
track name="SL727 MspIRRBS" GM12878_Rep7_RRBS MspIRRBS" visibility=2
name="SL727 MspIRRBS"
chr1 100001359 100001360 GM12878_Rep7_RRBS 1 + 100001359
100001360 0,255,0 1 0
chr1 100001384 100001385 GM12878_Rep7_RRBS 1 + 100001384
100001385 255,0,0 1 100
chr1 1000170 1000171 GM12878_Rep7_RRBS 52 + 1000170 1000171 105,255,0 52
15
chr1 1000190 1000191 GM12878_Rep7_RRBS 52 + 1000190 1000191 55,255,0 52
8
```

GEO Accession; Download. Data for two replicates in single bp resolution.

1. GSM683906; [D002]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeHaibMethylRrbs/wgEncodeHaibMethylRrbsGm12878HaibSitesRep1.bed.gz>

2. GSM683927; [D003]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeHaibMethylRrbs/wgEncodeHaibMethylRrbsGm12878HaibSitesRep2.bed.gz>

Histone modification ChIP-seq

Description of Broad Institute data:

https://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTables?db=hg19&hgta_group=regulation&hgta_track=wgEncodeBroadHistone&hgta_table=wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H2azStdPk&hgta_doSchema=describe+table+schema

Suggested visualization parameter: score (column 5)

Example lines of Broad Institute data:

chr22	16850291	16851951	.	643	.	6.190799	100.0	-1
chr22	16853758	16854340	.	602	.	5.696002	2.8	-1
chr22	16855214	16856146	.	587	.	5.513265	7.0	-1
chr22	16856291	16856836	.	609	.	5.778568	2.5	-1

Description of University of Washington data:

https://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTables?db=hg19&hgta_group=regulation&hgta_track=wgEncodeUwHistone&hgta_table=wgEncodeUwHistoneGm12878H3k27me3StdPkRep1&hgta_doSchema=describe+table+schema

Suggested visualization parameter: signal value (column 7)

Machine learning [H001-H003, H006, H009-H011, H0014-H017]: column 7 + bigwig signal value, peak mean, peak sum, peak fraction, signal mean

Example lines of University of Washington data:

chr1	713300	713450	.	0	.	91	112.768	-1	-1
chr1	713500	713650	.	0	.	25	26.7181	-1	-1
chr1	713880	714030	.	0	.	81	77.4798	-1	-1
chr1	714180	714330	.	0	.	32	106.565	-1	-1

H2A.Z

1. GSM733767 Broad Institute [H001]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H2azStdPk.broadPeak.gz>

Signal file

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H2azStdSig.bigWig>

H3K27ac

1. GSM733771 Broad Institute [H002]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k27acStdPk.broadPeak.gz>

Signal file

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k27acStdSig.bigWig>

H3K27me3

1. GSM733758 Broad Institute [H003]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k27me3StdPkV2.broadPeak.gz>
Signal file
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k27me3StdSigV2.bigWig>
2. GSM945196 Rep1 University of Washington [H004]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeUwHistone/wgEncodeUwHistoneGm12878H3k27me3StdPkRep1.narrowPeak.gz>
3. GSM945196 Rep2 University of Washington [H005]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeUwHistone/wgEncodeUwHistoneGm12878H3k27me3StdPkRep2.narrowPeak.gz>

H3K36me3

1. GSM733679 Broad Institute [H006]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k36me3StdPk.broadPeak.gz>
Signal
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k36me3StdSig.bigWig>
2. GSM945212 Rep1 University of Washington [H007]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeUwHistone/wgEncodeUwHistoneGm12878H3k36me3StdPkRep1.narrowPeak.gz>
3. GSM945212 Rep2 University of Washington [H008]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeUwHistone/wgEncodeUwHistoneGm12878H3k36me3StdPkRep2.narrowPeak.gz>

H3K4me1

1. GSM733772 Broad Institute [H009]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k04me1StdPkV2.broadPeak.gz>
Signal
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k4me1StdSig.bigWig>

H3K4me2

1. GSM733769 Broad Institute [H010]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k4me2StdPk.broadPeak.gz>
Signal
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k4me2StdSig.bigWig>

H3K4me3

1. GSM733708 Broad Institute [H011]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k04me3StdPkV2.broadPeak.gz>
Signal
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k04me3StdSigV2.bigWig>
2. GSM945188 University of Washington [H012]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeUwHistone/wgEncodeUwHistoneGm12878H3k4me3StdPkRep1.narrowPeak.gz>
3. GSM945188 University of Washington [H013]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeUwHistone/wgEncodeUwHistoneGm12878H3k4me3StdPkRep2.narrowPeak.gz>

H3K79me2

1. GSM733736 Broad Institute [H014]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k79me2StdPk.broadPeak.gz>
Signal
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k79me2StdSig.bigWig>

H3K9ac

1. GSM733677 Broad Institute [H015]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k9acStdPk.broadPeak.gz>
Signal
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k9acStdSig.bigWig>

H3K9me3

1. GSM733664 Broad Institute [H016]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k9me3StdPk.broadPeak.gz>
Signal

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H3k9me3StdSig.bigWig>

H4K20me1

1. GSM733642 Broad Institute [H017]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H4k20me1StdPk.broadPeak.gz>

Signal

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHistone/wgEncodeBroadHistoneGm12878H4k20me1StdSig.bigWig>

Transcription factor ChIP-seq

ENCODE Uniform Peaks description (Processing type 1):

https://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTables?db=hg19&hgta_group=regulation&hgta_track=wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform&hgta_table=wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Atf2sc81188V0422111UniPk&hgta_doSchema=describe+table+schema

Example lines:

chr2	88899531	88900071	.	1000	.	556.644232292884	-1
	4.7237265085109	290					
chr19	42772318	42772798	.	1000	.	447.745944254712	-1
	4.7237265085109	239					
chr1	28974824	28975695	.	1000	.	441.812803322091	-1
	4.7237265085109	365					

Suggested visualization parameter: score (column 5)

Machine learning [T001]...[T102]: column 7 peak mean, peak sum, peak fraction

Standard ChIP-seq Peaks from ENCODE/SYDH description (Processing type 2)

<http://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTrackUi?db=hg19&g=wgEncodeSydhTfbs>

Example lines:

chrX	11810449	11811790	.	1000	.	122.14865	300.0	300.0	790
chrX	13104757	13106706	.	1000	.	46.7399	300.0	300.0	
	1098								
chrX	18873837	18875147	.	1000	.	271.68327	300.0	300.0	559
chrX	19881040	19882430	.	1000	.	70.1822	300.0	300.0	767

Suggested visualization parameter: score (column 5)

Data with ENCODE Uniform Peak assigned:

Name UCSC_Accession Download

ATF2 wgEncodeEH002306 [T001]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Atf2sc81188V0422111UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

ATF3 wgEncodeEH001562 [T002]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Atf3Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

BATF wgEncodeEH001479 [T003]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878BatfPcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

BCL11A wgEncodeEH001486 [T004]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Bcl11aPcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

BCL3 wgEncodeEH001658 [T005]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Bcl3V0416101UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

BCLAF1 wgEncodeEH001563 [T006]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Bclaf101388V0416101UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

BHLHE40 wgEncodeEH002025 [T007]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Bhlhe40clggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

BRCA1 wgEncodeEH001830 [T008]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Brca1a300lggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

CEBPB wgEncodeEH003212 [T009]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Cebppsc150V0422111UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

CHD1 wgEncodeEH002823 [T010]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Chd1a301218alggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

CHD2 wgEncodeEH001831 [T011]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Chd2ab68301lggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

CTCF wgEncodeEH000029 [T012]
[denPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsBroadGm12878CtcfUniPk.narrowPeak.gz](http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsBroadGm12878CtcfUniPk.narrowPeak.gz)

CTCF wgEncodeEH000394 [T013]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUwGm12878CtcfUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

CTCF wgEncodeEH001851 [T014]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Ctcfsc15914c20UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

CTCF wgEncodeEH000532 [T015]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUtaGm12878CtcfUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

E2F4 wgEncodeEH002867 [T016]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878E2f4lggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

EBF1 wgEncodeEH001832 [T017]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Ebf1sc137065UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

EBF1 wgEncodeEH001480 [T018]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Ebf1sc137065Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

EGR1 wgEncodeEH002328 [T019]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Egr1Pcr2xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

ELF1 wgEncodeEH001617 [T020]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Elf1sc631V0416101UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

ELK1 wgEncodeEH002851 [T021]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Elk112771lggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

EP300 wgEncodeEH002037 [T022]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878P300bUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

EP300 wgEncodeEH002824 [T023]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878P300lggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

EP300 wgEncodeEH001487 [T024]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878P300Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

ETS1 wgEncodeEH001564 [T025]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Ets1Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

EZH2 wgEncodeEH002411 [T026]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsBroadGm12878Ezh239875UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

FOS wgEncodeEH000622 [T027]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878CfosUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

FOXM1 wgEncodeEH002529 [T028]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Foxm1sc502V0422111UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

GABPA wgEncodeEH001462 [T029]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878GabpPcr2xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

IKZF1 wgEncodeEH002811 [T030]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Ikzf1iknuclaUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

IRF4 wgEncodeEH001484 [T031]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Irf4sc6059Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

JUND wgEncodeEH000639 [T032]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878JundUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

MAX wgEncodeEH002806 [T033]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878MaxlggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

MAZ wgEncodeEH002852 [T034]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Mazab85725lggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

MEF2A wgEncodeEH001565 [T035]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Mef2aPcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

MEF2C wgEncodeEH001648 [T036]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Mef2csc13268V0416101UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

MTA3 wgEncodeEH002329 [T037]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Mta3sc81325V0422111UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

MXI1 wgEncodeEH002026 [T038]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Mxi1lggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

MYC wgEncodeEH000547 [T039]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUtaGm12878CmycUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

NFATC1 wgEncodeEH002307 [T040]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Nfatc1sc17834V0422111UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

NFE2 wgEncodeEH001808 [T041]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Nfe2sc22827UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

NFIC wgEncodeEH002343 [T042]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Nficsc81335V0422111UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

NFYA wgEncodeEH002064 [T043]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878NfyalggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

NFYB wgEncodeEH002065 [T044]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878NfyblggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

NR2C2 wgEncodeEH000697 [T045]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Tr4UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

NRF1 wgEncodeEH001846 [T046]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Nrf1lggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

PAX5 wgEncodeEH001489 [T047]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Pax5c20Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

PAX5 wgEncodeEH001495 [T048]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Pax5n19Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

PBX3 wgEncodeEH001477 [T049]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Pbx3Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

PML wgEncodeEH002308 [T050]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Pmlsc71910V0422111UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

POLR2A wgEncodeEH000626 [T051]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Pol2UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

POLR2A wgEncodeEH000708 [T052]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Pol2IggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

POLR2A wgEncodeEH001858 [T053]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Pol2s2IggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

POLR2A wgEncodeEH000592 [T054]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUtaGm12878Pol2UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

POLR2A wgEncodeEH001463 [T055]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Pol2Pcr2xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

POLR2A wgEncodeEH001517 [T056]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Pol24h8Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

POLR3G wgEncodeEH000645 [T057]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Pol3UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

POU2F2 wgEncodeEH001475 [T058]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Pou2f2Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

RAD21 wgEncodeEH000749 [T059]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Rad21IgrabUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

RAD21 wgEncodeEH001640 [T060]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Rad21V0416101UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

RCOR1 wgEncodeEH002841 [T061]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Corestsc30189IggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

RELA wgEncodeEH000690 [T062]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878NfkbTnfalgrabUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

REST wgEncodeEH002314 [T063]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878NrsfPcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

RFX5 wgEncodeEH001810 [T064]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Rfx5200401194IggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

RUNX3 wgEncodeEH002330 [T065]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Runx3sc101553V0422111UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

RXRA wgEncodeEH001541 [T066]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878RxaPcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

SIN3A wgEncodeEH002868 [T067]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Sin3anb6001263lggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

SIX5 wgEncodeEH001542 [T068]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Six5Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

SMC3 wgEncodeEH001833 [T069]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Smc3ab9263lggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

SP1 wgEncodeEH001496 [T070]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Sp1Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

SPI1 wgEncodeEH001476 [T071]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Pu1Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

SRF wgEncodeEH001464 [T072]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878SrfPcr2xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

STAT1 wgEncodeEH001852 [T073]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Stat1UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

STAT3 wgEncodeEH001811 [T074]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Stat5asc74442V0422111UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

STAT5A wgEncodeEH002321 [T075]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Stat5asc74442V0422111UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

TAF1 wgEncodeEH001478 [T076]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Taf1Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

TBL1XR1 wgEncodeEH002853 [T077]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Tblr1ab24550lggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

TBP wgEncodeEH001798 [T078]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878TbplggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

TCF12 wgEncodeEH001485 [T079]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Tcf12Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

TCF3 wgEncodeEH002315 [T080]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Tcf3Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

USF1 wgEncodeEH001468 [T081]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Usf1Pcr2xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

USF2 wgEncodeEH001812 [T082]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Usf2lggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

WRNIP1 wgEncodeEH001787 [T083]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878WhiplggmusUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

YY1 wgEncodeEH000695 [T084]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Yy1UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

YY1 wgEncodeEH001657 [T085]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Yy1sc281Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

ZBTB33 wgEncodeEH001488 [T086]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Zbtb33Pcr1xUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

ZEB1 wgEncodeEH001645 [T087]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsHaibGm12878Zeb1sc25388V0416102UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

ZNF143 wgEncodeEH001853 [T088]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Znf143166181apUniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

ZNF274 wgEncodeEH001756 [T089]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Znf274UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

ZZZ3 wgEncodeEH000698 [T090]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Zzz3UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

Data with Standard ChIP-seq Peaks from ENCODE/SYDH assigned:

CUX1(CDP) [T091]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeSydhTfbs/wgEncodeSydhTfbsGm12878Cdpsc6327lggmusPk.narrowPeak.gz>

ESRRA [T092]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeSydhTfbs/wgEncodeSydhTfbsGm12878ErralgrabPk.narrowPeak.gz>

FAM48A [T093]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeSydhTfbs/wgEncodeSydhTfbsGm12878Spt20StdPk.narrowPeak.gz>

IRF3 [T094]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeSydhTfbs/wgEncodeSydhTfbsGm12878Irf3lggmusPk.narrowPeak.gz>

KAT2A(GCN5)[T095]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeSydhTfbs/wgEncodeSydhTfbsGm12878Gcn5StdPk.narrowPeak.gz>

MAFK [T096]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeSydhTfbs/wgEncodeSydhTfbsGm12878MafklggmusPk.narrowPeak.gz>

SREBP1 [T097]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeSydhTfbs/wgEncodeSydhTfbsGm12878Srebp1lggrabPk.narrowPeak.gz>

SREBP2 [T098]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeSydhTfbs/wgEncodeSydhTfbsGm12878Srebp2lggrabPk.narrowPeak.gz>

ZNF274 [T099]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgTfbsUniform/wgEncodeAwgTfbsSydhGm12878Znf274UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

ZNF384 [T100]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeSydhTfbs/wgEncodeSydhTfbsGm12878Znf384hpa004051lggmusPk.narrowPeak.gz>

Data without combined replicates:

CREB1 (Rep 1) [T101]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeHaibTfbs/wgEncodeHaibTfbsGm12878Creb1sc240V042211PkRep1.broadPeak.gz>

CREB1 (Rep 2) [T102]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeHaibTfbs/wgEncodeHaibTfbsGm12878Creb1sc240V042211PkRep2.broadPeak.gz>

Open chromatin DNase-seq

Data description:

https://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTrackUi?hgsid=561795937_jVEsl5EEwrXniKOQX5ead2GZ1Aj3&c=chr7&q=wgEncodeDNaseSuper

DNase Hypersensitivity data description:

<http://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTrackUi?db=hg19&g=wgEncodeAwgDnaseUniform>

Machine learning [O001]: column 7, peak mean, peak sum, peak fraction

[O002, O006] - column 7, bigwig signal x2, peak mean, peak sum, peak fraction, signal mean

Download: [O001]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgDnaseUniform/wgEncodeAwgDnaseUwdukeGm12878UniPk.narrowPeak.gz>

Download: [O006] - peaks from different analysis pipeline

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeOpenChromDnase/wgEncodeOpenChromDnaseGm12878Pk.narrowPeak.gz>

Signal 1 - [O006s1]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeOpenChromDnase/wgEncodeOpenChromDnaseGm12878Sig.bigWig>

Signal 2 - [O006s2]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeOpenChromDnase/wgEncodeOpenChromDnaseGm12878BaseOverlapSignal.bigWig>

Open chromatin FAIRE-seq

FAIRE-seq data description

https://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTrackUi?hgsid=561779245_gadHNsG3pzt6A3OwqrWCOYobw32l&c=chr7&q=wgEncodeOpenChromFaire

Download: [O002]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeOpenChromFaire/wgEncodeOpenChromFaireGm12878Pk.narrowPeak.gz>

Signal 1 [O002s1]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeOpenChromFaire/wgEncodeOpenChromFaireGm12878Sig.bigWig>

Signal 2 [O002s2]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeOpenChromFaire/wgEncodeOpenChromFaireGm12878BaseOverlapSignal.bigWig>

Open chromatin ENCODE synthesis

ENCODE synthesis of evidence from different assays: DNaseI hypersensitivity (HS), Formaldehyde-Assisted Isolation of Regulatory Elements (FAIRE), and chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP) for select regulatory factors (PolII, CTCF, c-Myc).

Data description:

<https://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTrackUi?db=hg19&q=wgEncodeOpenChromSynth>

Example lines:

chr1	10166	10376	FAIREOnly_1	1000	.	10166	10376	153,0,0	0.99	0.00160	0.00
	0.01580	1.68	0.02650	1.51	0.00840	0.00	0.03360	0.00	3		
chr1	91363	91505	ChIPOnly_1	1000	.	91363	91505	255,0,255		0.24	
0.01320	0.62	0.00320	0.00	0.00000	0.00	0.22470	3.79	0.01890	0.00	4	
chr1	237659	237873	ChIPOnly_2	1000	.	237659	237873	255,0,255		0	
0.00570	0.00	0.00220	0.00	0.00150	0.00	0.21420	3.62	0.00000	0.00	4	
chr1	521439	521613	ChIPOnly_3	1000	.	521439	521613	255,0,255		0.52	
0.02080	1.05	0.00300	0.00	0.00120	0.00	0.45450	7.33	0.00000	0.00	4	
chr1	545991	546181	ChIPOnly_4	1000	.	545991	546181	255,0,255		0	
0.00110	0.00	0.00000	0.00	0.00130	0.00	0.17650	3.03	0.01410	0.00	4	
chr1	713841	714424	Valid_1	1000	.	713841	714424	0,0,0	11.17	0.17830	11.00
0.01560	1.65	0.14410	9.54	0.13180	2.33	0.05530	2.18	1			

Suggested visualization threshold and parameter: only three categories from column 4: Valid, OpenChrom, ChIPOnly

Machine learning [O003]:1 for all regions (binary), peak sum, peak fraction

Download: [O003]

<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeOpenChromSynth/wgEncodeOpenChromSynthGm12878Pk.bed.gz>

ATAC-seq

Data are not from ENCODE

Data description:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSE47753>

“Peak files are in UCSC broadPeak format, which includes the following columns: chromosome, start, stop, name, arbitrary score (1000), strand, read count within peaks, $-\log_{10}(1-\text{posterior probability})$, $-\log_{10}(\text{qvalue})$.”

Suggested visualization parameter: read count within peaks (column 7) peak mean, peak sum, peak fraction

Example lines:

chr1	9976	10725	id.1	1000	+	212	15.95458977019100	16.000000000000000
chr1	235351	235950	id.2	1000	+	78	3.74332637619407	4.95770682345444
chr1	564976	570525	id.3	1000	+	2985	15.95458977019100	16.000000000000000
chr1	713701	714750	id.4	1000	+	268	15.95458977019100	16.000000000000000

1. GSE47753 [O004]

<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/download/?acc=GSE47753&format=file&file=GSE47753%5FGM12878%5FATACseq%5F50k%5FAllReps%5FZINBA%5Fpp08%2Ebed%2Egz>

Machine learning [O004]: read count within peaks (column 7)

single cell ATAC-seq

PMID: 26083756

1. GSE65360 [O005]

<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/download/?acc=GSE65360&format=file&file=GSE65360%5Fsingle%2DGM12878%2Epeaks%2Ebed%2Egz>

Suggested visualization parameter: None

Machine learning [O005]:1 for all regions (binary) peak sum, peak fraction

Example lines:

chr1	713880	714380
chr1	762641	763141
chr1	805000	805500

ENCODE genome segmentation

Discrete annotation maps of regulatory regions and other chromatin elements.

Description:

<http://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTrackUi?db=hg19&g=wgEncodeAwgSegmentation>

PMID: 23221638

Example lines:

chr1	10000	10271	CTCF	1000	.	10000	10271	10,190,254
chr1	10400	10605	T	1000	.	10400	10605	0,176,80
chr1	10605	15800	R	1000	.	10605	15800	127,127,127
chr1	15800	18820	T	1000	.	15800	18820	0,176,80
chr1	18820	109711	R	1000	.	18820	109711	127,127,127

Suggested visualization parameter: segment category (column 4)

Machine learning [S001-S003]: 1 for all regions (binary) in the category, fraction

S001 categories: active, repressed

S002, S003, S004 categories: heterochromatin, active, repressed

Active - 1 for all regions but repressed

1. Combined Download [S001]:
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgSegmentation/wgEncodeAwgSegmentationCombinedGm12878.bed.gz>
2. ChromHMM [S002]:
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgSegmentation/wgEncodeAwgSegmentationChromhmmGm12878.bed.gz>
3. Segway [S003]:
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeAwgSegmentation/wgEncodeAwgSegmentationSegwayGm12878.bed.gz>
4. ChromHMM, only histone marks [S004]:
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeBroadHmm/wgEncodeBroadHmmGm12878HMM.bed.gz>

RNA-seq

Data description:

https://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTrackUi?hgsid=561843471_QiMzI3fxEUmLTIBkmKEeNP0a4NAi&c=chr7&g=wgEncodeCshlShortRnaSeq

“Contigs (continuous regions covered by uniquely aligned reads) are in BED9 format. The Contigs represent blocks of overlapping mapped reads from the pooled biological replicates. FORMAT: 9 \t seperated columns. 1-6: BED 7: Bases per Kilobase per Million mapped bases

(BPKM) 8: non-parametric irreproducible discovery score (npIDR) between the replicates 9: Total mapped bases. The bedscore (column 5) is computed as $\min(1000, 100 * \log(\text{summed_bpm} * 100 + 1))$.”

Example lines:

chr1	244085	244163	contig_12	254	+	0.115	0.58	228
chr1	325159	325261	contig_18	282	+	0.148	0.30	403
chr1	462046	462240	contig_25	306	+	0.201	0.09	986

Suggested threshold: npIDR (column 8) < 0.1

Suggested visualization parameter: bed_score (column 5)

Machine learning [R001-R012]: column 7 with column 8 < 0.1, contig mean, contig sum, contig fraction over loop/anchor.

Experiments (GEO accession; Name \t Download):

1. GSM758572; whole cell polyA- [R001]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeqGm12878CellPamContigs.bedRnaElements.gz>
2. GSM758559; whole cell polyA+ [R002]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeqGm12878CellPapContigs.bedRnaElements.gz>
3. GSM767852; cytosol polyA- [R003]
[http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeqGm12878CytosolPamContigs.bedRnaElements.g
z](http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeqGm12878CytosolPamContigs.bedRnaElements.gz)
4. GSM758560; cytosol polyA+ [R004]
[http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeqGm12878CytosolPapContigs.bedRnaElements.g
z](http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeqGm12878CytosolPapContigs.bedRnaElements.g
z)
5. GSM984605; nucleolus total [R005]
[http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeqGm12878NucleolusTotalContigs.bedRnaElement
s.gz](http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeqGm12878NucleolusTotalContigs.bedRnaElement
s.gz)
6. GSM767853; nucleus polyA- [R006]
[http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeqGm12878NucleusPamContigs.bedRnaElements.
gz](http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeqGm12878NucleusPamContigs.bedRnaElements.
gz)
7. GSM765386; nucleus polyA+ [R007]
[http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeqGm12878NucleusPapContigs.bedRnaElements.g
z](http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlLongRnaSeqGm12878NucleusPapContigs.bedRnaElements.g
z)

8. GSM605625; TAP-only whole cell small [R008]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlShortRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlShortRnaSeqGm12878CellShorttotalTapContigs.bedRnaElements.gz>
9. GSM977042; TAP-only chromatin small [R009]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlShortRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlShortRnaSeqGm12878ChromatinTapContigs.bedRnaElements.gz>
10. GSM605627; TAP-only cytosol small [R010]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlShortRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlShortRnaSeqGm12878CytosolShorttotalTapContigs.bedRnaElements.gz>
11. GSM977032; TAP-only nucleolus small [R011]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlShortRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlShortRnaSeqGm12878NucleolusTapContigs.bedRnaElements.gz>
12. GSM605633; TAP-only nucleus small [R012]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeCshlShortRnaSeq/wgEncodeCshlShortRnaSeqGm12878NucleusShorttotalTapContigs.bedRnaElements.gz>

Repli-seq

“Peaks - Local maxima in the wavelet-smoothed signal data corresponding to replication initiation (replication origin) zones. Higher replication time score (column 5, range 0-1000) correspond to earlier replication. Peak span is set to 1kb.”

Suggested visualization parameter: Replication time score (column 5).
 Machine learning [P001]: column 5, mean of all origins in a loop/anchor

Example lines:

chr1	227500	228500	.	600	+	.	.	179,45,0
chr1	620500	621500	.	700	+	.	.	179,45,0
chr1	986500	987500	.	1000	+	.	.	179,45,0
chr1	1745500	1746500	.	900	+	.	.	179,45,0

1. GSE51334 [P001]
<http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeUwRepliSeq/wgEncodeUwRepliSeqGm12878PkRep1.bed.gz>

GRO-cap, GRO-seq transcription start sites from nascent RNA

Suggested visualization parameter: None

Example lines:

```
chr1 896250      896310      M1    0    +
chr1 901850      901880      M1    0    +
```

1. GSE60456, processed TSS are in tss_all_gm12878.bed [N001] file in Supplementary Data Set to the publication <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/25383968>
<http://www.nature.com/ng/journal/v46/n12/extref/ng.3142-S2.zip>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM1480326>

https://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/samples/GSM1480nnn/GSM1480326/suppl/GSM1480326_GM12878_GROseq_minus.bigWig [N001_minus.bw]

https://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/samples/GSM1480nnn/GSM1480326/suppl/GSM1480326_GM12878_GROseq_plus.bigWig [N001_plus.bw]

Machine learning [N001]: 1 for all regions (binary) , peak sum, peak fraction

Bru-seq - nascent RNA sequencing

1. GSM1347660 [N002]
<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/download/?acc=GSM1347660&format=file&file=GSM1347660%5FGM128780h1%2Esegments%2Ebed%2Eqz>

“supplementary_files_format_and_content: segments.bed = extended BED format file, one record for each HMM transcription segment, where column 4 is a unique identifier for the corresponding fused and revised transcription unit in format chrom:start-end(strand), column 5 is always 0, column 7 is the segment’s HMM state (0..9), column 8 is segment RPKM, and columns 9 is the transcription unit RPKM.”

Suggested threshold: HMM state > 2 (column 7);

Suggested visualization parameter: HMM state (column 7)

Machine learning [N002]: column 8 with column 7 > 2; peak mean, peak sum, peak fraction

Example lines:

```
chr1 9500 13500 NA 0 + 9 0 NA
chr1 14500 16500 NA 0 + 8 0 NA
chr1 46500 549500 NA 0 + 0 0 NA
chr1 558500 565500 NA 0 + 3 0 NA
chr1 565500 566453 NA 0 + 7 1.81379 NA
chr1 566453 568136 chr1:566453-568136(+) 0 + 7 1.81379 3.90816
```

chr1	568136	569075	chr1:568136-569075(+)	0	+	7	1.81379	0.041571
------	--------	--------	-----------------------	---	---	---	---------	----------

Supplementary Text 2: Theory of Fisher's Linear Discriminant Analysis

Let's consider a set of n samples of d dimensions as

$$X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{n_1}, X_{n_1+1}, \dots, X_n$$

such that $D_1 = \{X_i \in \omega_1 : i = 1, 2, \dots, n_1\}$ and $D_2 = \{X_i \in \omega_2 : i = n_1 + 1, n_1 + 2, \dots, n\}$, where ω_1 and ω_2 are two classes.

Let w denote the normal to a hyperplane H . Now, if $\|w\| = 1$ the orthogonal projection of X onto H may be obtained as

$$y_i = w^t \cdot X_i$$

So, the mean of samples of class ω_1 is

$$m_1 = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{\forall X \in D_1} X$$

Similarly, the mean of samples of class ω_2 is

$$m_2 = \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{\forall X \in D_2} X$$

where $n_2 = n - n_1$. Then, the sample means for the projected space $R_1 = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{n_1}\}$ and $R_2 = \{y_{n_1+1}, y_{n_1+2}, \dots, y_n\}$ may be obtained as

$$\tilde{m}_1 = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{\forall y \in R_1} y = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{\forall X \in D_1} w^t X = \frac{1}{n_1} w^t \sum_{\forall X \in D_1} X = w^t m_1$$

$$\tilde{m}_2 = w^t m_2$$

So, the distance between projected means

$$|\tilde{m}_1 - \tilde{m}_2| = |w^t m_1 - w^t m_2| = |w^t (m_1 - m_2)|$$

It signifies that by scaling w , separability between ω_1 and ω_2 may be increased. However, separability is relative to scatter of X .

Now, scatter in the projected space may be obtained as

$$\tilde{s}_i^2 = \sum_{\forall y \in R_i} (y - \tilde{m}_i)^2$$

Hence, the total within-class scatter in the projected space is

$$\tilde{s}_1^2 + \tilde{s}_2^2$$

Now, a criterion function may be introduced as

$$J(w) = \frac{|\tilde{m}_1 - \tilde{m}_2|^2}{\tilde{s}_1^2 + \tilde{s}_2^2}$$

It is now evident that $J(w)$ needs to be maximized for better separability in the projected space.

Scatter matrix of samples of set D_i is

$$S_i = \sum_{\forall X \in D_i} (X - m_i)(X - m_i)^t$$

Total within-class scatter matrix is

$$S_W = \sum S_i = S_1 + S_2$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{s}_i^2 &= \sum_{\forall y \in R_i} (y - \tilde{m}_i)^2 \\ &= \sum_{\forall X \in D_i} (w^t X - w^t m_i)^2 = \sum_{\forall X \in D_i} w^t (X - m_i)(X - m_i)^t w \\ &= w^t \left[\sum_{\forall X \in D_i} (X - m_i)(X - m_i)^t \right] w = w^t S_i w \end{aligned}$$

So, we can write

$$\tilde{s}_1^2 + \tilde{s}_2^2 = w^t S_1 w + w^t S_2 w = w^t S_W w$$

Similarly

$$|\tilde{m}_1 - \tilde{m}_2|^2 = (w^t m_1 - w^t m_2)^2 = w^t (m_1 - m_2)(m_1 - m_2)^t w = w^t S_B w$$

where S_B = Between-class scatter

So, $J(w)$ reduces as

$$J(w) = \frac{w^t S_B w}{w^t S_W w}$$

This is an expression of Rayleigh quotient. For Rayleigh quotient, w that maximizes $J(\bullet)$ must satisfy

$$S_B w = \lambda S_W w, \text{ where } \lambda \text{ is a constant}$$

As S_B is in the direction of $m_1 - m_2$, we can write

$$S_B w = k(m_1 - m_2), k \text{ is a scale factor}$$

Hence,

$$k(m_1 - m_2) = \lambda S_W w$$
$$w = k/\lambda S_W^{-1}(m_1 - m_2)$$

Here, k/λ can be ignored since we are interested in the direction of w . So,

$$w = S_W^{-1}(m_1 - m_2)$$

Finally, Fisher's linear discriminant hyperplane is given by $w^t X = 0$ and projection is taken as $y = w^t X$ where y is a scalar quantity obtained for each X .

Supplementary Table 1: ANOVA table for each trajectory parameter

percolation model	SS	df	F	p
slope				
model	3036.26	9	13.15	0.000
residual	4259.81	166		
critical region width				
model	13.04	9	64.88	0.000
residual	3.71	166		
onset				
model	1.31	9	173.03	0.000
residual	0.14	166		
bias				
model	1.61	9	12.33	0.000
residual	2.41	166		

Supplementary Text 3: Pairwise comparisons between models for each trajectory parameter.

Supplementary Table 2: Pairwise comparisons between models for slope and critical region width. All p-values are Bonferroni-corrected.

model 1	model 2	slope		critical region width	
		t	p	t	p
AE	CA(1)	21.284	0.000	-9.520	0.000
AE	CC(1)	9.004	0.000	-6.242	0.000
AE	CLa(1)	11.843	0.000	-4.022	0.016
AE	CLa(2)	20.849	0.000	-20.136	0.000
AE	CLb(1)	11.056	0.000	-17.246	0.000
AE	CLb(2)	-2.336	1.000	0.825	1.000
AE	ER	4.406	0.003	-8.653	0.000
AE	LF	-4.631	0.002	10.266	0.000
AE	TE	-4.109	0.008	6.365	0.000
CA(1)	CC(1)	-2.929	0.247	2.971	0.220
CA(1)	CLa(1)	-4.342	0.006	2.482	0.842
CA(1)	CLa(2)	1.050	1.000	3.476	0.069
CA(1)	CLb(1)	-0.024	1.000	-5.833	0.000
CA(1)	CLb(2)	-3.438	0.076	6.418	0.000
CA(1)	ER	-19.488	0.000	9.025	0.000
CA(1)	LF	-7.109	0.000	11.163	0.000
CA(1)	TE	-23.579	0.000	9.900	0.000
CC(1)	CLa(1)	-0.271	1.000	0.382	1.000

CC(1)	CLa(2)	2.718	0.480	0.807	1.000
CC(1)	CLb(1)	1.821	1.000	-8.535	0.000
CC(1)	CLb(2)	-3.146	0.164	4.273	0.008
CC(1)	ER	-7.132	0.000	5.685	0.000
CC(1)	LF	-6.399	0.000	8.121	0.000
CC(1)	TE	-11.094	0.000	6.669	0.000
CLa(1)	CLa(2)	4.953	0.003	0.207	1.000
CLa(1)	CLb(1)	2.187	1.000	-6.351	0.000
CLa(1)	CLb(2)	-2.178	1.000	2.737	0.571
CLa(1)	ER	-10.208	0.000	3.613	0.048
CLa(1)	LF	-4.504	0.004	5.399	0.000
CLa(1)	TE	-13.755	0.000	4.334	0.006
CLa(2)	CLb(1)	-0.512	1.000	-9.187	0.000
CLa(2)	CLb(2)	-2.439	1.000	5.092	0.003
CLa(2)	ER	-21.196	0.000	18.029	0.000
CLa(2)	LF	-5.102	0.001	19.471	0.000
CLa(2)	TE	-21.734	0.000	21.842	0.000
CLb(1)	CLb(2)	-2.385	1.000	10.769	0.000
CLb(1)	ER	-9.635	0.000	16.828	0.000
CLb(1)	LF	-4.955	0.001	18.409	0.000
CLb(1)	TE	-12.677	0.000	17.569	0.000
CLb(2)	ER	2.530	0.752	-1.579	1.000
CLb(2)	LF	0.237	1.000	1.785	1.000
CLb(2)	TE	2.116	1.000	-0.249	1.000
ER	LF	-5.070	0.000	13.174	0.000
ER	TE	-8.475	0.000	15.341	0.000
LF	TE	4.132	0.008	-8.095	0.000

Supplementary Table 3: Pairwise comparisons between models for onset and bias. All p-values are Bonferroni-corrected.

model 1	model 2	onset		bias	
		t	p	t	p
AE	CA(1)	17.716	0.000	-5.296	0.000
AE	CC(1)	5.602	0.000	-6.583	0.000
AE	CLa(1)	8.921	0.000	1.543	1.000
AE	CLa(2)	-87.721	0.000	3.772	0.031
AE	CLb(1)	3.391	0.086	-3.697	0.038
AE	CLb(2)	-17.020	0.000	-9.922	0.000
AE	ER	10.751	0.000	2.821	0.327
AE	LF	-28.263	0.000	-18.490	0.000
AE	TE	-8.928	0.000	-3.005	0.201
CA(1)	CC(1)	-10.560	0.000	0.258	1.000
CA(1)	CLa(1)	1.345	1.000	4.018	0.016
CA(1)	CLa(2)	-27.956	0.000	5.220	0.001
CA(1)	CLb(1)	-3.058	0.205	-2.551	0.716
CA(1)	CLb(2)	-21.040	0.000	-1.710	1.000
CA(1)	ER	-14.781	0.000	5.682	0.000
CA(1)	LF	-32.015	0.000	-1.359	1.000
CA(1)	TE	-19.727	0.000	4.916	0.001
CC(1)	CLa(1)	6.446	0.000	4.661	0.003
CC(1)	CLa(2)	-23.508	0.000	6.009	0.000

CC(1)	CLb(1)	1.537	1.000	-2.655	0.559
CC(1)	CLb(2)	-17.276	0.000	-2.327	1.000
CC(1)	ER	-2.032	1.000	7.090	0.000
CC(1)	LF	-24.534	0.000	-2.121	1.000
CC(1)	TE	-8.120	0.000	6.083	0.000
CLa(1)	CLa(2)	-12.531	0.000	1.324	1.000
CLa(1)	CLb(1)	-2.514	0.927	-2.711	0.605
CLa(1)	CLb(2)	-12.941	0.000	-5.723	0.001
CLa(1)	ER	-7.728	0.000	-1.061	1.000
CLa(1)	LF	-16.698	0.000	-8.445	0.000
CLa(1)	TE	-9.752	0.000	-2.019	1.000
CLa(2)	CLb(1)	8.234	0.000	-3.018	0.306
CLa(2)	CLb(2)	-5.988	0.000	-6.541	0.000
CLa(2)	ER	79.591	0.000	-3.360	0.094
CLa(2)	LF	-0.870	1.000	-9.633	0.000
CLa(2)	TE	82.968	0.000	-4.177	0.010
CLb(1)	CLb(2)	-10.066	0.000	1.441	1.000
CLb(1)	ER	-2.295	1.000	3.774	0.031
CLb(1)	LF	-11.207	0.000	2.354	1.000
CLb(1)	TE	-4.162	0.010	3.622	0.047
CLb(2)	ER	18.068	0.000	10.377	0.000
CLb(2)	LF	7.542	0.000	1.430	1.000
CLb(2)	TE	16.252	0.000	9.472	0.000
ER	LF	-31.368	0.000	-19.455	0.000
ER	TE	-18.669	0.000	-5.810	0.000
LF	TE	25.832	0.000	17.529	0.000